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Impact of Emerging Technologies on Future Employment Opportunities at United States

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Abstract

Robots, artificial intelligence, machine learning are transforming human life. People are worried about the impact of development of technology on their jobs. Therefore, there is a strong need to determine how emerging technologies are going to affect future employment opportunities and their benefits. This particular study explored the impact of these emerging technologies on workforce. If society needs to cut off jobs due to robotics, many social benefits delivered through jobs are also affected. There are many questions raised for public policy because of emerging technologies which impact on various demographic works. As a result, there is a need to confirm social contract for new economy to deliver social benefits which are unfolding.

Keywords: Technology, Employment Opportunities, Robotics, Artificial Intelligence, Economy

Introduction

The current approaches will be insufficient when it is linked with fulltime jobs employment patterns. Changing society needs fewer workers to perform basic tasks. Already there is an impact on the blue collar jobs and it started spreading towards white collar jobs. Because of emerging technology more jobs are affected and more positions are made obsolete (James Manyika, 2013).

In this situations there is a need to think about the ways for people to get healthcare benefits, pensions outside of fulltime employment, offering basic benefits, income tax, credit benefits, activities for lifetime educations, expanding profit sharing benefits are the ways to represent this. There is a need to circular in schools too so that students will be trained for the jobs which are existing. So that we can expand their horizons throughout their lives. Economies need to determine the ways to avoid employment possibilities.

The emerging technologies which is growing every day. Robots, artificial intelligence, machine learning technologies have ability to transform existing business and personal lives. They are making people easy to improve their personal and business dealings. Technology is becoming sophisticated which impact workforce (Andra, 2015).

Robotics

Robots are expanding themselves around the developed world. The figure.1 shows number of industrial robots in global market in the past few years. For example in 2013 there is a use of 1.2 million approximately and it increased to 1.5 million in 2014. In 2017 it has been increased to 1.9 million.

Japan is the largest country in the world which uses Robotics and the second place goes to North American and china takes third place and forth place goes to South Korea and 5th place goes to Germany. Where the usage of robotics are mentioned in the numbers in the below table (Daniela, 2015).

Country	Robotics (In use)
Japan	3,06,700
North America	2,37,400
China	1,82,300
South Korea	1,75,600
Germany	1,75,200

According to RBC global assessment study(2014) the costs of the robots have fallen substantially. Auto industry is the place where robots restricted their use to few high wage industries. However, robots now placed as alternative to labor. In this magic world there are many robots that perform complex functions. A key factor that shows the ability of robots to correctly understand and respond accordingly to the speech and underlying content. For example, in Japan there is a hotel named Hem-na which uses robots to take reservation and they speak Japanese and English according to the choice of customer (Beatrice, 2015). Amazon has organized picking challenge like robots grab the items from a shelf and put in tub. The company is already using 15,000 robots to do this work and it expects few more to buy in future (Mike, 2015).

Artificial Intelligence

Machines that respond to the consistent traditional responses from humans who has given the capacity of judgment and intension referred as artificial intelligence. This has been used in different fields such as finance transportation, telecommunications, healthcare, energy department (Shukla, 2013). By its extra ordinary processing power of computers, humans implement owns skills to improve productivity through artificial intelligence.

Machine Learning

Machine to machine communications is nothing but controlling the sensors that removes from the equations and substituted by automated process which has become very popular in healthcare sector. Automated machines are being targeted more in the healthcare sector (James, 2015). Robots help the humans to personalize their treatment and deal with health, safety. Robots will help to improve the life quality through interactivity and social ability. In connection with wired ‘smart phones’ it is possible to integrate robots in day to day lives of senior citizens to improve their medical treatment (Martin Ford, 2015).

Impact on the Workforce

Rapid increase of technologies suggest that they are having impact on workforce. Many tech companies have achieved broad economies without employees in a large scale. For example if we take Google is it worth of \$370 billion but only 5500 employees are working at the moment(Derek, 2015). Not only in tech filed there are number of fields where technology is replacing labor, and this affect the middle class jobs and incomes. (Harold, 2013) argues that common understanding since longtime was that technology is destroying jobs but also creates a new ones. Now the problem is technology is destroying the existing jobs indeed creating a new era. (Martin ford, 2015) argues that “As technology accelerates machine automation will affect the

economy to the extent that wages no longer provide consumers with adequate income and confidence in future. If this issue is not raised it may affect the result and downward economic spiral. He also warns that in future after many decades machines will be able to do jobs in large percentage where average people of this population may not be able to find new jobs.

Firms have been already using the robots, artificial intelligence, and machine learning to replace humans and improve their productivity and efficiency in terms of operations. During the recession many business has to downsize the labor for some financial issues (Thi,2016). For example: one of the manufacturing company had 500 workers for \$100 million now they have the same size of workforce even though company has grown up to \$250 million in revenues. He did this by using robots in certain functions and advanced manufacturing techniques to operate the firm (Philip, 2015).

Figure 2: Future employment projections by sector, 2012-2022 (in millions)

The above diagram gives a picture of the employment projections. In the recent analysis it is predicted that 15.6 millions have new positions which are created between 2012 to 2022. This growth is about 0.5% of labor force. In healthcare sector the growth increases by 2.6% this will create 5 million new jobs in future decade. Other areas like construction will increase by 1.6 million, state and local government 9,29,000 and professional services jobs by 3.5 million(Harold, 2013). Oxford university researchers Calfrey and Michael Osborn claim that technology will transform in many factors. They found 47% of U.S. workers have high probability of seeing their jobs automated over next 20 years. According to their analysis, tele marketers, insurance, tax preparers, library techniques have 99% of their jobs computerized. On the other hand if we consider occupational therapists, social workers have less than 1% chance of their task to be computerized. However even some researchers recognize that many jobs will be lost through emerging technology, but they say new jobs will be created (Carl, 2013).

Even though machines are soughting in warehouses better than humans many jobs like analyzing bigdata, data sharing networks will be created. In future decades even though, work will be transformed but still humans need to manage digital world. For example MIT economist (David,2015) Author has analyzed data on jobs and technology but “Doubt that can technology can bring abrupt change in total employment”. (Richard Freeman, 2016) argues that “technology world change wide range of jobs fast enough to explain recent job numbers. (Robert Garden, 2016) take a stand by this statement and argues that recent progress in computing and automation is less transformative then electrician even indoor plumbing. Based on this arguments the dramatic workforce effects from emerging technologies see the substitution of technology for labor. Research center study asked 1,896 experts and found that 48% of experts envision a future with robots, digital agents offered blue and white color jobs that lead to increase income inequality and breakdown in the social order(Erik, 2014). Another people looked in to the opinion of the public on technology and found that emerging technology revealed that 65% of them think it would change their lives if robots come in place. In addition people have been on the emerging technology for driverless cars. When surveyed 48% of people said they would love to have driverless whole 50% answered they couldn’t (Daniela, 2015).

Workforce Effects on Various Demographic Groups

Across all the demographics technology doesn’t play equally across all groups. It will depend on gender, income and race and ethnicity. Within the development of technology and their ramifications in workforce make some of the individuals in to risk. It is quite clear that technical skills specially trades will face rough going in future. But the complications are not limited only to young people. With the aging population jobs towards healthcare appear to insulate people employed in these areas from technological change (Philip, 2015). Yet digital technology is changing caregiving. Racial minorities face dismal job opportunities even in the best of times. Already minorities, poor people have high unemployment rates. Without a training it will be difficult for them to adapt new economy where advanced machines take their jobs. An analysis of digital inequality shows that many of these individuals lack access to high speed internet which creates difficulties for

them in education and employment too. That limits their ability to adapt to the emerging realities of the 21st century workforce (James, 2015).

Implications of Public Policy

According to Edward Bellmeay people stopped working in US at the age of 45 and devote their lives to mentoring people and contribution to senses of community. There are very short week works where the people receives full benefits, food, housing. In flash forwarding of the current era, robotics and machine learning have been improved productivity and enhanced the overall economy of developed nations. Overall economic performance is invested in innovation to see tremendous growth. In future, it may be possible that society will not need as many workers as seen today. In this section, I reviewed short and long-term steps that should be considered to deal the emerging technologies. This includes to deliver the benefits outside jobs, basic income guarantee, retraining, profit sharing, benefit credits to volunteerism (Harold, 2013).

Encourage Corporate Profit Sharing

In an analysis of the American economy, there are several problems that are harming working benefits. This includes business investment , compensation,. They also note problems related to stock buybacks, quarterly earnings, rise of the activist investors. The concern of this paper over impact of emerging technologies on employment possibilities because of robotics and machine learning where the economic problems suggests that we need to think about how to deliver the social benefits and make sure large number of people are not left behind permanently. One of the long-term option is to encourage the corporate profit sharing both for fulltime and part-time. A challenge of the current situations is how-to provide financial support for the few worker's in terms of benefits. Profit sharing represents different ways to spread benefits of improved productivity to a broader group of people. Companies need to provide 5000\$ in share profits for employees who are making at least 50,000\$ per year. This would improve work wages and share more corporate profits. It won address the problems of people without jobs but it would encourage greater equity among the larger cross sections of population.

Benefits of Outside Jobs

In future if we end up with a situation with many people who are unemployed and underemployed for a certain period of time there is a need to provide them pension benefits outside the employment called as flexible security. It orders healthcare education and housing assistance. Currently the people need to work 60% of their rime in order to qualify for fulltime benefits. When they are fully employed companies provide healthcare plans and pensions. During the period world war 2 people with limited skills were able to get well playing jobs in factories, warehouses, they could educate their children the complication came when economy shifted. In regard to retirement planning, many employers have moved to 401-style pension plans. Employees contribute to their own funds and sometimes get a match from the employer. But this does not help those outside the workforce who need retirement assistance. Even Social Security is tied to employment. People who haven't worked are not eligible for retirement benefits so we need to figure out ways to take care of those people in the newly emerging economy.

Benefits of Voluteerism

The trends cited in the analysis suggest that there is a need to consider income supplements through fulltime jobs. One possibility that comes through volunteer activities. A variety of survey evidence demonstrates that young people are interested in volunteerism (James, 2015). For example, a survey of American students found that they want “ a Job that focus on helping others and improving society”. A number of them value volunteer activities outside of their work experience. They have varied interests and want extra circular activities to fulfil them. According to Deloitte study 63% of millennials donate to charities and 43% actively volunteer as a member of community organization. In the digital world where there may be less work more leisure time, it makes sense to think about incentives and work credits for volunteerism. This could include credits towards social benefits that acknowledge community contributions (Daniela, 2015). In future people likely to have more time outside of employment so it makes sense to encourage them towards community engagement and give them incentives to volunteer non-profit organizations. This will benefit overall community and give people purposeful activities to engage.

Next Steps

To summarize, advanced societies are at a major turning point in terms of how they think about work, leisure and social benefits. If advanced economies need fewer workers to complete needed tasks and benefits which are delivered through fulltime jobs, there is a danger that many people face difficulties in getting healthcare pensions and income maintenance to sustain their lives. There is a need for people to live fulfilling lives even if society needs relatively few workers. We need to think about various ways to address these issues before we have permanent underclass of unemployed individuals. Thee needs to be continuous learning opportunities for arts and outcome to supplement incomes and benefits other than fulltime jobs. Policies must encourage volunteerism and reward for those who contribute to worthy causes which make sense from the society as a whole. Adoption of these steps will help people to adapt to new economic realities.

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